

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3402729

UDC Classification: 331.108.26: 65.012.8

JEL Classification: M 54

PERSONNEL SECURITY OF THE INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISE: ITS ESSENCE, CONSTITUENTS AND MEASURES OF MINIMIZATION OF THREATS

КАДРОВА БЕЗПЕКА ПРОМИСЛОВИХ ПІДПРИЄМСТВ: СУТНІСТЬ, СКЛАДОВІ ТА ЗАХОДИ МІНІМІЗАЦІЇ ЗАГРОЗ

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Recieved 12.02.2019

Смоквіна Г.А., Янковська О.А. Кадрова безпека промислових підприємств: сутність, складові та заходи мінімізації загроз. Науково-методична стаття.

У статті визначено сутність кадрової безпеки, розглянуто підходи щодо її визначення, досліджені та запропоновані ключові складові кадрової безпеки, їх підвиди (безпека праці, технологічна безпека, адміністративна безпека, естетична безпека, протиконфліктна безпека, кар'єрна безпека), надано визначення складовій «протиконфліктна безпека». Розглянуто загрози кадрової безпеки, їх класифікацію, з урахуванням яких запропоновано комплекс заходів з мінімізації загроз кадрової безпеки промислових підприємств та організаційні напрями зміцнення кадрової складової економічної безпеки. Імплементація цих заходів та напрямів зміцнення кадрової безпеки дозволить промисловим підприємствам зменшити або мінімізувати ризики, що пов'язані із кадровою безпекою, створити позитивний клімат у колективі, збільшити продуктивність праці.

Ключові слова: кадрова безпека, складові кадрової безпеки, загрози

Smokvina G.A., Yankovska O.A. Personnel security of the industrial enterprise: essence, components and measures of threats minimization. Scientific and methodical article.

The article defines the essence of personnel security, examines approaches to its definition, examines and suggests key components of personnel security, their subspecies (labour safety, technological safety, administrative safety, aesthetic safety, anti-conflict security, career safety), defines the component "anti-conflict security". The personnel security threats, their classification, on the basis of which have been proposed a set of measures to minimize threats to personnel security of industrial enterprises and organizational directions to strengthen the personnel component of economic security, have been considered. The implementation of these measures and directions for strengthening personnel security will allow industrial enterprises to reduce or minimize the risks associated with personnel security, create a positive climate in the team, and increase labour productivity.

Keywords: personnel security, personnel security components, threats

One of the important factors in the potential growing and the competitiveness increasing of modern industrial enterprises is an effective management system. Globalization processes, European development trends and modern changes in the domestic economy make entrepreneurs look for new means to ensure an effective economic security system and counteracting external and internal threats. The successful functioning of modern enterprises depends on the availability of rational measures to ensure their safety, since the main threats and risks are related to employees or staff that are both a source of threats and a personnel security object. That is why the important component of economic security is the personnel security of industrial enterprises.

Analysis of recent research and publications

In order to protect against abuses, searching for solutions to the issues of crime prevention in the economy, delinquencies related to an enterprise employees, increasing of staff capacity and loyalty determines deep and systematic research of personnel security at modern industrial enterprises.

A significant contribution to the research of business entities personnel security was made both by the following domestic and foreign scientists, such as: Arkhipov E.L. (Arkhipov, 2016), Bashynska I.O., Honcharova K.H., Zapara A.P., Kovtunenکو Yu.V, Kroklicheva H.Ye. (Kroklicheva, 2016), Svitlychna V.Yu, Slipa O.Z., Shyra T.B. and others. The investigations of these scholars highlight: the relationship of financial and economic and personnel security as a component, the main objectives, objects and subjects of personnel security are disclosed, delinquencies in the field of personnel security are investigated, etc.

As indicated by the analysis of investigated domestic and foreign sources, the issue of developing measures to minimize the personnel security threats of industrial enterprises and the directions of strengthening the economic security personnel component have not been sufficiently studied.

Unsolved aspects of the problem

In spite of considerable attention to the proposed subject, the personnel security components are limited to several subsets, organizational security measures are limited to personnel control or scattered by numerous threats. The main threats to personnel security of industrial enterprises, measures for their minimization and organizational strengthening have not given attention.

The aim of the article is to consider the essence of personnel security, components and their subspecies, an overview of approaches to its definition and classification of threats. On the basis of the undertaken study, to identify the most significant personnel security threats, to provide a set of measures to minimize them and to propose strengthening directions.

The main part

Increasing the role of employee management in the the enterprise management, liberalizing the labour market and democratizing the society contribute to the growing role of personnel security. Verification and rational decisions choice in order to ensure the economic security of the enterprise and its optimization is a complicated process. Therefore, an effective organized policy in the personnel sphere allows to reduce significantly possible enterprise losses.

At present, there is no generally accepted definition of the "personnel security", the main differences in the interpretation of this concept among scholars are the consideration of personnel security as a security, as a process, as a component of economic security, etc., through the use of authors approaches by each scholar. Let's bring them into the tab. 1.

The definitions analysis of the concept "personnel security" is given in tab. 2.

Table 1. Definitions of the concept "Personnel security"

Author	Definition
S.V. Danylenko [1]	Under personnel security it is meant the state of the economic entity security from personnel hazards and threats, or interpreted as a process of preventing negative effects on the economic security of enterprises by eliminating the risks and threats associated with personnel, its intellectual potential and labour relations in general
O.F. Yaremenko [2]	Personnel security characterizes the presence of the most efficient enterprise staffing structure, in which the effective functioning of all the economic system components, the security and the ability to withstand the internal and external influences related to personnel, provides mutual satisfaction of their interests and development
A.Yu. Romanko [3]	Personnel security is the process of preventing, minimizing and monitoring external threats to staff and internal threats associated with staff.
T.L. Zubko, V.V. Laptieva [4]	Personnel security can be defined as a functional component of economic security, which is a characteristic of enterprises interests security from threats that are directly related to actions or staff inactivity
Gh. O. Tkachuk [5]	Personnel security is the main functional component of the enterprise economic security which involves the preservation and intellectual potential development of an enterprise, effective personnel management
T.V. Momot, Chzhan Khaoui, D.T. Momot [6]	Personnel security is a synthetic category of economic theory, staff management, management sociology and labour economics, which is defined as an activity to create conditions for the stable functioning and an enterprise development, which ensures the protection of the the enterprise interests from the risks and threats associated with its own employees and staff itself from internal and external threats such as blackmail, gambling with competitors, attacks on life and health of employees, etc.
T.S. Bushman [7]	Personnel security is a process of preventing destabilizing influences on the part of the staff, the priority task of which is to create conditions for the enterprise security to ensure its effective functioning.
S.P. Mishchenko [8]	Under the intellectual and personnel security of enterprises should be understood the characteristics of an enterprise state, in which all areas of intellectual and staff work, a set of principles, methods, staff management mechanism aimed at detecting, neutralizing, averting, precaution and preventing threats, hazards and risks directed at staff and its intellectual potential
I.O. Tarasenko, K.S. Filimoniuk [9]	Personnel security is the process of preventing or minimizing the impact on a company's economic security by eliminating the threats associated with an enterprise staff
O.Yu. Chorna, A.H. Vysokolenko [10]	Personell security is not a result, but a constant process of preventing undesirable actions by personel that can harm the enterprise
A.M. Morozova, A.O. Lysenko [11]	Personnel security is an element of economic security of enterprises, provided that it contains all stages of the saff torganization and management, aimed at establishing labour and social and cultural relations, providing a breakeven enterprise activity
M.A. Molchanov [12]	The "personnel security" concept is a process of preventing negative effects on the company's economic security at the expense of risks and threats associated with staff, its intellectual potential and labour relations in general
V.L. Pozdieiev [13]	Personnel security is a process of the threats prevention to the economic security of enterprises associated with the staff actions and labour relations in the team.

Source: own elaboration

Table 2. Analysis of the definitions of the concept of "personnel security"

Criterion	Sources												
	[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]	[5]	[6]	[7]	[8]	[9]	[10]	[11]	[12]	[13]
Security state	+												
The process of preventing negative effects / undesirable actions / destabilizing impacts	+						+		+	+		+	+
Availability of the most effective enterprise staffing structure		+											
The prevention, minimization and monitoring process			+										
Functional component / economic security element				+	+						+		
Synthetic category						+							
Activities on creating conditions for a stable functioning and an enterprise development						+							
An enterprise condition rating								+					

Source: own elaboration

Most authors (national and foreign) hold to the opinion that personnel security is a process of preventing negative influences or unwanted actions or destabilizing influences on the financial and economic security of the enterprise, expected from the personnel (staff), in order to improve its functioning.

Also, personnel security should be considered as a combination of its components. The personnel security components are shown in fig. 1

Let's characterize each constituent:

- workers' health safety includes creating safe working conditions, minimizing injury production and occupational diseases.
- physical security includes the measures implementation aimed at preventing the external hazards appearance among workers or members of their families.
- work safety involves creating safe working conditions.
- technological safety is contained in using of advanced experience and the introduction of modern technologies and equipment.
- administrative security is contained in the staffing capacity identification and control and consistent, objective evaluation of work results.
- intellectual security is contained in increasing of employees' professional skills and knowledge, stimulating the personnel initiative, innovations for the personnel development.
- informational security includes the definition of the need for staff, its attraction and placement, the structure prediction and the results evaluation of the relevant work; the improvement of professional knowledge and skills, abilities.
- Aesthetic security is revealed in conducting educational seminars and discussions, and of employees' satisfaction with their work due to the motivation.
- Financial security is associated with ensuring the staff confidence at the work place and the payment stability in line with the qualifications and quality of the performed work.
- anti-conflict security is concerned with the using of diplomatic measures to avoid internal corporate divisions and tensions in a violent conflict. Conflict prevention measures include precaution, information collection and careful analysis of the factors that are the driving force behind the conflict.
- patriotic security is revealed when creating a positive and friendly psychological climate among employees and personnel unification around the general objectives of an enterprise.
- psychological and communication security includes consistency, non-conflict in communication at different levels, helping each other, positive microclimate in the enterprise.
- pensionable and insurance security are related to social protection, insurance of personnel (medical and pension)
- career security is related to the staff promotion in training and self-actualization during work.

All the personnel security components are considered as a system of interconnected interconnections and are the elements of one system.

The most important part of an HR manager's job is the personnel security provision at the industrial enterprise. Both internal and external threats need to be analyzed. Threats to personnel security in the field of their emergence are shown in tab. 3.

Fig. 1. Personnel security components combination and their subtypes
 Source: compiled by the authors on the materials [14-15]

Table 3. Classification of personnel security threats

Internal		External
– insufficient educational level or personnel qualification – poorly organized personnel management system and training system, – the existence of an ineffective incentive system – lack of corporate policy or its non-rationality – Incorrect examinations during hiring, – the number of rational and innovative proposals reduction or their absence, – dismissal of skilled personnel, – mistakes in employee resource planning; – having no interest in respecting the corporate interests		– better working conditions and effective incentive system from competitors – competitors’ readiness to entice other personnel, – pressure on employees outwardly, – the presence of changes in the economic environment, – in particular, inflation processes; – appearance of a staff’s external dependencies (for example from competitors)
Related to a particular employee or personal	Related to the staff features	
– theft of property, – disclosure of information (for example, through negligence), – damnification to an enterprise reputation, – company’s important specialists dismissal a or their conflicts, – threats to the life and health of owners and (or) key specialists; – discreditation in the management system	– strikes, – mass dismissals, – resistance to an enterprise requirements, – negligence of of its values and norms, – sabotage, – insubordination, – imitating professional behavior	

Source: own elaboration

As we see from the table, the impact consequences of the personnel security threats on the enterprise are not the objectives achievement, but strategic stability violations, economic security disruption in general, staff turnover, official crimes, and others.

The above circumstances encourage the enterprise management to build a set of measures aimed at monitoring, timely detection and elimination (or minimization) of threats to the normal enterprise functioning.

According to the scientific studies [1-17] the most significant threats to the personnel security have been analyzed and identified (tab. 4).

Table 4. The statistical analysis of personnel security threats

The threat name	% of respondents surveyed
Intervention with enterprise resources	15
Conflicts formation	25
Misbehavior and deterioration of discipline, safety, internal labour regulations	30
Illegal implementation activity at the enterprise	20
Others	10

Source: own elaboration

Based on the analysis results, we will present measures to minimize the most significant threats to personnel security of industrial enterprises in fig. 2.

In order to counterstand the threats to personnel security, it is also appropriate to identify areas that contribute to its strengthening. The searching these directions requires a systematic and detailed definition of the nature, essence, personnel security components and the interrelationships identification between them.

Fig. 2. A set of measures to minimize personnel security risks of industrial enterprises
Source: own elaboration

In order to implement the proposed measures to minimize threats, it is efficient to investigate and determine the organizational directions of strengthening personnel security at industrial enterprises.

In the investigated scientific sources [3; 16; 17] have been already considered similar measures to strengthen personnel security. However, in order to ensure an effective process of forming and strengthening the staffing component, it is possible, due to more detailed schedule of them, to the corresponding organizational directions as shown in fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Organizational directions of strengthening the personnel component of economic security
Source: compiled by the authors on the materials [3, 16, 17]

In order to provide personnel security, other measures may also be recommended: the personnel safety for hiring in conjunction with staff management; maintenance plans for safety, taking into account the risks identified by the inspection authorities; list of safety assessment positions; contact reporting; postsale service; continuous training on security issues; personnel distribution management.

Conclusions

The conducted theoretical and analytical research has determined that staff is a key subject of threats that can damage information, financial and property components of economic security of industrial enterprises. Investigated and proposed key personnel security components and their subspecies (labour safety, technological, administrative security, aesthetic safety, anti-conflict security, career safety). Definition of the component "anti-conflict security" is given.

A common threats classification is considered, on the basis of which the most significant personnel security threats are revealed. The complex of measures for threats minimization and organizational directions of strengthening the personnel component of economic security is offered. Implementation of these measures and directions of strengthening personnel security will allow industrial enterprises to reduce or minimize the risks associated with personnel security, to create a positive climate in the team and to increase labour productivity.

Among the prospects for further explorations in this area, it is advisable to carry out a study of existing indicators and methods of personnel security assessment among which determine the most significant and most influential.

Abstract

Among the weighty factors of potential growth and competition improvement of modern industrial enterprises is an effective management system. Globalization processes, European development directions and modern changes in the domestic economy are forcing entrepreneurs to look for new means of ensuring an effective economic security system and countering external and internal threats. The successful functioning of modern enterprises depends on the availability of rational measures to ensure their security, since the main threats and risks associated with personnel or personnel are both a source of threats and an object of personnel security. That is why an important component of economic security is personnel security of industrial enterprises. The purpose of the article is to examine the essence of personnel security, the components and their subspecies, a review of approaches to its definition and classification of threats. On the basis of the conducted research, to identify the most significant threats to personnel security, to bring a set of measures to minimize them and to suggest strengthening directions.

The conducted theoretical and analytical research has determined that staff is a key subject of threats that can damage information, financial and property components of economic security of industrial enterprises. Investigated and proposed key personnel security components and their subspecies (labour safety, technological safety, administrative security, aesthetic safety, anti-conflict safety, career security). Definition of the component "anti-conflict security" is given.

A common threats classification is considered, on the basis of which the most significant personnel security threats are revealed. A set of measures to minimize threats and organizational directions to strengthen the personnel component of economic security are proposed (audit, analysis of performance indicators, control over personnel selection and their status, clear record keeping; the regulation of employee relations and supervision, promoting and increasing loyalty, team cohesion; monitoring of communications and relations among workers, checking personnel for belonging to risk groups, prevention and timely resolution of conflicts, clear regulation of the schedule; documentation audit, tracking and monitoring communications in the company, mandatory documentation of any business transactions). These measures implementation and directions for strengthening personnel security, industrial enterprises will be able to reduce or minimize the risks associated with personnel security, create a positive climate in the team and increase productivity. Among the prospects for further explorations in this area, it is advisable to carry out a study of existing indicators and methods of personnel security assessment among which determine the most significant and most influential.

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Посилання на статтю:

Smokvina G. A. Personnel security of the industrial enterprise: essence, components and measures of threats minimization / G. A. Smokvina, O. A. Yankovska // Економічний журнал Одеського політехнічного університету. – 2019. – № 1 (7). – С. 38-45. – Режим доступу до журн.: <https://economics.opu.ua/ejopu/2019/No1/38.pdf>. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3402729.

Reference a Journal Article:

Smokvina G. A. Personnel security of the industrial enterprise: essence, components and measures of threats minimization / G. A. Smokvina, O. A. Yankovska // Economic journal Odessa polytechnic university. – 2019. – № 1 (7). – С. 38-45. – Retrieved from <https://economics.opu.ua/ejopu/2019/No1/38.pdf>. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3402729.

